

Evaluation of structural vulnerabilities in DNA origami nanoplat- forms using ionizing radiation

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DNA origami holds great promise as a platform for diverse nanostructure assemblies, but its long-term stability remains a key challenge, especially in application-specific environments. In this study, we used two types of ionizing radiation to controllably induce strand breaks in three distinct DNA origami shapes, simulating long-term damage and identifying structural weak points. Damage was assessed using atomic force microscopy (AFM), agarose gel electrophoresis (AGE), and melting point analysis. AFM revealed that overall structural integrity was retained even after exposure to extremely high radiation doses. However, melting point measurements showed a reduction in thermal stability, indicating an increased number of strand breaks, supported by AGE analysis of denatured samples. Vulnerabilities were most pronounced at exposed edges and single-stranded regions, which are more accessible to reactive species generated during water radiolysis. This approach offers a simple method to identify DNA origami weak points and probe long-term stability of DNA nanostructures in a fast and controlled way. The results also provide benchmarks for theoretical models and guidelines for the design of robust DNA origami for various applications.

1 Introduction

DNA origami nanostructures as a scaffold for assembling nanoscale architectures have been extensively explored for many types of applications. Their unique property of site addressability of functionalizable sites ensures precise arrangement of multiple components in nano-architectural designs inaccessible to common bottom-up approaches [1–4]. The stability of DNA origami is crucial to maintain the integrity of the assembly in respective application-specific environments [5–7]. Current thrusts to use them as sensing and diagnostic devices [8–10], nanophotonics [11, 12], and as platforms for DNA data storage [13] necessitate evaluation of long-term stability and prediction of eventual degradation hotspots that could be triggered down the line. This informs strategies of structural reinforcement to make structures more stable in the long term without losing their desired properties.

Two approaches could be applied to enhance DNA nanostructure stability. The first relies on chemical and surface modifications of the nanostructures [14], aiming to improve stability beyond that inherent to DNA. Examples include photo-induced [15] and covalently bound [16] cross-links, as well as a variety of encapsulation strategies ranging from polymeric or oligopeptide coatings to silicification [17–19].

The second approach focuses on the rational design of highly rigid DNA nanostructures. Several design “weak points” have been identified in the past, and strategies to achieve highly stable structures have been proposed by modifying scaffold routing and staple crossovers to produce more compact designs, or by creating three-dimensional multilayer structures [20–22]. However, improving designs requires systematic exploration of vulnerabilities, optimization of design procedures, and experimental benchmarking. To identify design flaws, controlled accelerated damage procedures similar to those used for polymeric materials could be employed. These are typically based on thermal structural degradation, which can be monitored using various techniques [23]. However, their application to DNA origami is limited to temperatures below ~ 60 °C due to its melting point [24]. Another option is controlled nicking by nucleases, introducing

incremental damage by adjusting concentration and incubation times, particularly relevant for biological applications [25]. In this work, we propose the use of ionizing radiation to induce accelerated damage to DNA nanostructures.

Although the interaction of radiation with matter is complex [26], its effects on DNA in realistic environments can generally be categorized as either direct or indirect [27]. Indirect effects usually dominate, reflecting the situation in biological systems, where copious free radicals are produced through radiolysis, while only a small fraction of ionizing particles from natural background radiation cause direct damage. Despite the stochastic nature of radiation–matter interactions, this approach has been used to identify weak points in DNA strands [28–31]. Here, we use radiation to incrementally induce strand breaks on DNA origami nanostructures, which at higher fluences, can eventually reveal structural weak points. We tested two ionizing radiation sources to represent different linear energy transfer (LET) regimes: low-LET electrons (16 MeV) and high-LET carbon ions (^{12}C , 1.14 GeV). The primary difference lies in their particle tracks, or the distribution of ionization events upon interaction with a volume of matter. At low LET, ionization events are more scattered and isolated, whereas at high LET, they are densely concentrated along the incident particle’s track, potentially causing clustered or complex nanoscale damage [32]. The various effects induced by different types of radiation radiation on DNA origami nanostructures have been profiled and discussed in a recent review article [31]. The primary effects of low LET are caused by secondary radical species, mainly by OH radicals [33]. The effects similar to chemical degradation or oxidative damage could therefore be expected [5, 34]. In the high-LET regime, such as in the case of ion beams, other types of damage can also be observed, including well-localized punctures typically around a 10-nm diameter around the ion track [35]. Using both radiation types allows profiling of different damage mechanisms, which could be customized to simulate application-specific situations. Such measurements can then help predict long-term damage and guide reinforcement, structural redesign, protective strategies, or even the optimal positioning of functional components.

Moreover, the resulting data can provide a benchmark for the development of new DNA nanostructure and radiation interaction modeling tools such as OxDNA [36] or CATANA [37], and GEANT 4 DNA [38] or MBN Explorer [39], respectively.

2 Results and Discussion

2.1 Radiation-induced structural damage

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) was employed to quantify the number of intact DNA origami nanostructures remaining after irradiation and to visualize nanoscale damage features. Damaged structures are identified based on deviations from the predicted shape. For triangles, damage typically appears as missing or damaged corners, broken trapezoidal domains, or occasionally distorted or denatured structures. For rectangular structures, common defects include chipped or peeled structures, often evident from a reduced length of the shorter side, and occasionally, distorted or denatured structures. For the Z/S-shape, typical damage includes chipped arms, bent or folded arms, and distorted or denatured forms. Fragments are usually paired or “puzzled” with a nearby complementary damaged structure to avoid counting the same damage multiple times. The damage classification is summarized in Figure 1A. Figure 1B shows the dose-dependent decrease in the mean percentage of intact structures for each of the three shapes, comparing control samples with those exposed to either electron or carbon ion radiation. Overall, the nanostructures demonstrate exceptional stability, showing only a slight reduction in the number of intact structures even at extremely high doses relative to the controls. The Z/S-shaped DNA origami is particularly sensitive to sample preparation and deposition conditions [40], leading to substantial variability in counting results and deviations from a linear dose–response trend.

Figure 1C presents the decay rates (σ_d) derived from linear fits to the dose–response curves. Triangular structures exhibit greater radiation sensitivity, with higher decay rates under high-LET carbon ion exposure than under low-LET electron irradiation. In contrast, rectangular and Z/S-shaped structures sustain similar levels of damage regardless of radiation type, indicating lower sensitivity to LET.

Figure 1: AFM damage count. Damage classification implemented for counting intact and damaged nanostructures (A); mean percentage of intact shapes (I) in AFM images of DNA origami samples irradiated with high energy electrons (B, filled shapes, solid line trend) and carbon ions (B, half filled shapes, dashed line trend); and the estimated decay rate ($\sigma_d \pm SE$) from the linear approximation to the absorbed dose (D) dependence of I (C).

Figure 2 depicts characteristic damage features in irradiated DNA origami, which appear comparable for both radiation types. In rectangular structures, damage primarily involves the separation of parallel DNA duplexes. It typically originates at the short edges containing unpaired single-stranded scaffold regions intentionally included to prevent aggregation. In Z/S-shaped structures, the short arms are most affected, frequently fragmenting due to strand breaks that propagate from single-stranded extensions at the edges, similar to the propagation pattern observed from the rectangular structures. In triangular structures, damage is concentrated at the corners, where single-stranded domains connect trapezoidal monomers—consistent with previous findings for gamma-irradiated 2D DNA origami triangles [33]. We posit that its stability in low-LET compared to the other two shapes is the fact that its damage-prone edges and single-stranded regimes are concealed at the vertices; however, in higher-LET, the additional contribution from more concentrated ionizing events along the direct path of the incident charged particle may propagate to larger areas on the nanostructures than just isolated nicks when they are along the path or vicinity of the particle track.

It is also worth noting that the observed damage propagation patterns resemble the observed real-time DNase I digestion of DNA origami [25] which points to accessibility-related mechanisms. In solution, most irradiation-driven structural damage is attributed to reactive secondary species such as OH radicals and low-energy secondary electrons, with site accessibility likely influencing the susceptibility of the structures to damage. Damage propagation patterns for the rectangular and Z/S-Shaped nanostructures is somehow consistent with this observation because lateral single-stranded domain breakage can begin to separate the

parallel duplexes, thereby leaving staple crossovers vulnerable to radical attack and further cleavage. However, given the radical yields estimated for the two irradiation types (Figure S4)—with electron irradiation producing roughly 2.5 times more OH radicals than carbon ions—the extent of damage likely also reflects direct particle interactions or track-specific effects. OH radical-driven processes are more closely linked to general scaffold degradation, as supported by agarose gel electrophoresis (AGE) and melting point data, which will be discussed in the following section.

Figure 2: Damage features. Representative AFM images of unirradiated DNA origami samples and those irradiated with high energy electrons (A) and carbon ions (B) with different absorbed doses.

2.2 Scaffold scission

Although the overall structural damage remains relatively low even at high absorbed radiation doses, multiple strand breaks can still occur within the DNA nanostructures with the only remaining crossovers holding the structure together. These breaks, particularly those occurring on the scaffold strand, can be detected using AGE and are often correlated with corresponding changes in melting temperature, providing insight into the extent of damage.

Two AGE runs were performed on aliquots of the irradiated samples: one with the sample analyzed directly as recovered after irradiation, and a second with a pre-denaturing step applied to disassemble the nanostructures prior to electrophoresis. Analysis of the non-denatured samples by AGE (Figure 3) in the case of the triangular and rectangular DNA origami supports AFM findings by showing strong, well-defined bands corresponding to intact nanostructures even up to the highest absorbed dose implemented. Only faint smearing, trailing bands indicative of minor damage were observed. For the Z/S-shape, however, this analysis is non-trivial because the nicked samples, although they appear mostly intact in AFM images, can be shredded electrophoretically even under milder AGE conditions (Figure S1).

Concerning the AGE results for the triangular nanostructures, it is known that they tend to aggregate under high magnesium ion (Mg^{2+}) concentrations, which results in immobile bands trapped within the gel wells [34]. Notably, irradiation promotes the disaggregation of these structures, as demonstrated by the dose-dependent decrease in the intensity of these immobile bands. At the highest doses, the smear on the intact nanostructure bands exhibit features consistent with the release of trapezoidal monomers, as previously observed from enzymatically degraded triangular nanostructures [25].

For denatured samples, the degree of nicking on the scaffold can be assessed by performing AGE without the MgCl_2 supplement in the running buffer. This approach revealed the state of the scaffold even when the

overall structure remains intact. Figure 3 shows the AGE profiles of denatured triangular and rectangular DNA origami. A similar AGE profile was also observed for the Z/S-shaped nanostructures (Figure S1). The estimated scaffold lengths, based on the average band mobilities of the scaffold (in the case of the control) and scaffold fragment band (in the case of irradiated samples) extracted from these gel images, are shown in Figure S2 to obtain a rough estimate of the degree of scaffold fragmentation. The same nicking could also occur among the staples but they are more difficult to visualize in AGE due to the small differences in lengths.

Regardless of shape, the extent of scaffold scission appears to be broadly similar across all nanostructures. However, subtle differences in the distribution of fragment sizes are evident. For example, at the highest irradiation doses, denatured triangular structures exhibit a narrower distribution of scaffold fragment sizes compared to the rectangular and Z/S-shaped nanostructures. This observation is consistent with the trailing patterns seen in the AGE profiles of non-denatured samples and may suggest, in the case of the triangles, that the scaffold fragments primarily originate from trapezoidal monomer units. However, the limited resolution of AGE prevents a more definitive interpretation of these features.

Regarding LET effects, scaffold scission is notably lower under carbon ion irradiation compared to electron irradiation, consistent with the reduced radical yields produced by carbon ions (Figure S4). It is important to note that the control samples used for carbon ion irradiation already exhibit partial scaffold degradation, as evidenced by AGE profiles of denatured samples (Figure 3) and scaffold fragment mobilities (Figure S2) because they had to stay at room temperature similar to the irradiated samples which were also only recovered 24 hours after the irradiation as part of safety measures. Nonetheless, the decay rates from this cumulative damage was lower during carbon ion irradiation compared to electron irradiation, reinforcing the dependence of nicking extent to radical yields.

To further understand the consequences of scaffold nicking, melting point measurements were performed on both unirradiated and irradiated DNA origami solutions. The dose dependence of melting points is summarized in Figure 4A, with the full melting curves shown in Figure S3. Estimated decay rates (σ_m) in melting temperature, derived from linear fits of the dose-response curves, are presented in Figure 4B, allowing comparison across different nanostructure shapes and radiation types.

For the triangular DNA origami, melting curves display two distinct peaks, likely reflecting the presence of aggregates (Peak 1, higher melting temperature) also observed in the AGE analysis of non-denatured samples, alongside monomeric triangular units (Peak 2, lower melting temperature). As expected, the melting temperature decreases with increasing nicking due to fragmentation of both scaffold and staple strands. Although all three nanostructures share the same scaffold sequence, their melting points differ, particularly in the case of the Z/S-shaped DNA origami, due to differences in the length distributions of their staple strands. Among the structures tested, the Z/S-shaped nanostructures show the greatest decrease in melting temperature following electron irradiation.

Regarding LET effects, and consistent with denaturing AGE results, nicking and melting point depression rates under carbon ion irradiation are lower than those under electron irradiation, likely due to differences in OH radical yields. Nicking on triangular and Z/S-shaped structures exhibit greater sensitivity to LET than rectangular structures. Overall, OH radical yields have a stronger impact on damage to scaffold strands and, consequently, on melting temperatures. However, in contrast to AFM evaluations of structural damage, design features and localized damage effects also play essential roles in preserving the overall shape upon irradiation.

3 Conclusion

We systematically evaluated radiation-induced damage in three DNA origami nanostructures using AFM, AGE, and melting point analysis. Our results reveal that ionizing radiation can serve as a practical tool for accelerated aging of DNA nanostructures, allowing the development of fast test protocols for emerging DNA technologies [5, 41]. More importantly, ionizing radiation can be used to identify vulnerabilities in DNA nanostructure design and to benchmark theoretical models. AFM imaging highlighted a striking shape-dependent response: triangular structures displayed exceptional stability under low-LET electron

Figure 3: AGE visualization of scaffold scission by irradiation. Gel images of triangular and rectangular DNA origami nanostructures irradiated with high energy electrons (left column) and carbon ions (right column). The images in the top row are from samples directly loaded to the gels after irradiation while those in the bottom row are from samples that were denatured before loading into the gels. The asterisk (*) marks possible band positions attributed to the triangular DNA origami’s trapezoidal fragments.

Figure 4: Irradiation-induced melting point depression. Absorbed dose (D) dependence of the melting point (T_m) of the different DNA origami shapes irradiated with high energy electrons and carbon ions (A) and the estimated rate of melting point decrease ($\sigma_m \pm SE$) extracted from the linear approximation of the absorbed dose dependence of T_m (B).

irradiation—where damage is dominated by sparsely distributed OH radical attacks—yet became similarly as vulnerable to high-LET carbon ion exposure as the rectangular and Z/S-shaped nanostructures. The behavior at low LET irradiation likely stems from the triangular shape’s closed geometry. The rectangular and Z/S-shaped DNA origami possess multiple edges where staple strands change direction; providing easily accessible radical attack sites. The triangular design exposes such features only at its vertices. This limited exposure not only enhances mechanical stability, as noted in Kosinski’s work [42], but also shields the structure from secondary reactive species generated in the surrounding medium. This has to be taken into account when designing DNA nanostructures for specific applications, such as in structure-based DNA

Figure 5: Scheme of damage initiation sites. Flat design of the three DNA origami shapes from cadnano and oxView renders highlighting sites of unpaired nucleotides (Top row). An unoptimized sketch of the origami shapes summarizing the typical damage patterns observed from AFM (Bottom row) with representative AFM images of 8 kGy electron-irradiated samples (diameter of circular cut-out = 400 nm).

data storage [43, 44], where shape-specific degradation may result in selective information losses. On the other hand, there are also potential applications of the phenomenon in sensorics or nanodosimetry, where radical yield or dose can be measured by monitoring the degradation of a specific DNA nanostructure shape in the mixture [45]. Under high-LET heavy ion irradiation, however, the concentrated, track-localized damage overwhelms these protective advantages, leading to similar degradation patterns across all shapes.

Damage signatures were consistently shape-dependent, often initiating at single-stranded or flexible regions where strand separation or breakage could propagate more readily. These mechanisms are summarized schematically in Figure 5. The results suggest that nanostructure geometry and the accessibility of susceptible sites critically influence how damage evolves, with broadly similar pathways emerging under both radiation types.

Complementary AGE and melting point measurements further confirmed that scaffold strand scission occurred even when AFM images suggested largely intact architectures. AGE profiles of denatured samples revealed broadly comparable fragmentation across shapes, with subtle differences in scaffold length distributions hinting at geometry-specific failure modes. LET effects were most clearly reflected in melting point depression and scaffold breakage patterns: carbon ion irradiation produced less fragmentation than electron exposure, consistent with its lower radical yield. Overall, these findings demonstrate that the interplay between direct radiation effects, clustered damage, and structural accessibility governs the degradation of DNA origami. They also highlight an intriguing avenue for computational modeling—mapping radical attack sites relative to ionization tracks—to better understand and predict how radiation damage propagates through these nanoscale architectures.

4 Experimental Section

4.1 DNA origami synthesis

Reaction mixtures containing 6 nM M13mp18 ssDNA scaffold (Tilbit Nanosystems), 60 nM DNA origami staple mix (Metabion) of the desired shape - 2D triangle [46], twist-corrected rectangle [47], or Z/S-shape [48] - were mixed in 1xTAE with 12.5 mM MgCl_2 (Sigma Aldrich). These mixtures were then annealed to 90 °C for 5 min and slowly cooled to 10 °C at a rate of $-7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in a heating block

equipped with temperature control [33]. To remove the excess staples, the mixtures were filtered through 100 kDa MWCO Amicon filters (Millipore) three times with additional 400 μL of 1xTAE with 12.5 mM MgCl_2 (which serves as both the folding and storage buffer) each time. The concentration of the filtered mixtures was estimated from their respective UV absorbance values at 260 nm using a Denovix DS-11 FX+ spectrophotometer. About 50 μL of 12-15 nM of DNA origami nanostructures are recovered after filtration. These were then reproduced and diluted to the desired concentrations for the irradiation experiments.

4.2 Electron irradiation

The Microtron MT25 accelerator of the Nuclear Physics Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences in Prague was used to generate monoenergetic 16 MeV electron beams with only tens of keV of beam spread. The details of the accelerator were already described previously [49]. DNA origami solutions of the desired shape (6 nM, 100 μL) in 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes were fixed in a rotating sample holder facing the beam exit 45 cm away. The dose rate was measured prior to irradiation using a TN34045 ionizing chamber (PTW Freiburg) and a Keithley 617 programmable electrometer. The dose rates were varied between 5 – 20 Gy s^{-1} , with the higher dose rates applied to the higher absorbed doses. The dose rates within the area of the sample holder only varied by $\pm 10\%$. Sample heating was prevented by the use of a cooling fan placed near the sample holder.

4.3 Carbon ion irradiation

The ^{12}C ion irradiation experiments were performed at the GANIL (Grand Accélérateur National d'Ions Lourds) facility in Caen, France within the IRABAT (IRradiation À Basse Temperature) beamline. The beamline features a dedicated dosimetry and a beam sweeping device capable of uniformly irradiating a typical irradiation field of 5 cm \times 5 cm with an ion fluence accuracy of $\sim 5\%$, horizontal frequency of 400 Hz, and vertical frequency of 4 Hz [50].

The DNA origami samples of the desired shape (6 nM, 100 μL) in 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes were fixed onto a dedicated sample holder and irradiated with 95 MeV u^{-1} or 1.14 GeV ^{12}C ion beam. The maximum flux was set to 1.3×10^8 ions $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ equivalent to 5.3 Gy s^{-1} . The ion flux was calculated from the measurement of the beam intensity using secondary electron emission-based detector made from a thin Fe foil placed inside the IRABAT vacuum chamber. The detector served as an online flux monitor during sample irradiation and was calibrated prior to irradiation using a Faraday cup.

4.4 Atomic force microscopy

Control and irradiated samples were deposited onto Si substrates (~ 0.5 cm \times 0.5 cm) that were plasma cleaned for 10-20 s using the Roplass RPS40+ plasma cleaner. This was done by placing a 1 μL drop of 6 nM of the desired DNA origami solution in the middle of the substrate succeeded by the addition of a 15 μL drop of 10xTAE solution with 125 mM MgCl_2 . The droplet was then allowed to incubate for 1 h over an ethanol bath. Afterwards, the surface of the substrate was washed with 1 mL of 50% ethanol solution and then thoroughly dried with N_2 gas. The imaging of the dried samples was performed in air using the Dimension Icon AFM (Bruker) PeakForce Tapping Technology with ScanAsyst probes (40 kHz, 0.4 N m^{-1}). Scans were acquired at a size of 3 μm \times 3 μm with 512 lines collected at a scan rate of 1 Hz. Image post-processing was carried out in Gwyddion software and limited to flattening and adjusting the color range to enhance the visibility of the structures against the background. Intact and damaged structures were annotated and counted using the Cell Counter plug-in in ImageJ. The mean percentages of intact nanostructures (\pm standard deviation) were evaluated from 4 - 14 images per absorbed dose. The number of images was adjusted to include approximately 1000 or more nanostructures per absorbed dose, across two independent irradiation experiments.

4.5 Agarose gel electrophoresis

The irradiated DNA origami samples together with the respective control samples were run in a 1% agarose gel at 100 V for 35 min immersed in a 0.5xTAE buffer with 12.5 mM MgCl₂. Each well contained 10 μ L of 1.5 nM DNA origami sample mixed with 2 μ L of 6x gel loading dye (ThermoFisher Scientific).

To check for scaffold fragmentation, another electrophoresis experiment was performed on another aliquot of the irradiated and control samples. In this case, the DNA origami samples were first melted by heating them to 75 °C enough to ensure staple-scaffold separation and then quickly quenched in an ice bath to avoid reassembly. The samples were loaded into a 1% agarose gel run at 100 V for 35 min immersed in a 0.5xTAE buffer without MgCl₂. Each well contained 10 μ L of 1.5 nM of melted DNA origami sample mixed with 2 μ L of 6x gel loading dye (ThermoFisher Scientific).

4.6 Melting curve measurement

Melting curves were measured using a fluorescent DNA intercalating dye-based method previously described [51]. Control and irradiated DNA origami samples were each diluted to 350 pM in 400 μ L with 0.35x SYBR Green I (ThermoFisher Scientific) and allowed to equilibrate in the dark for 30 min. The solutions were transferred into a quartz cuvette and the fluorescence was measured at an emission wavelength of 524 nm and excitation wavelength of 497 nm using an Edinburgh FS5 spectrofluorometer equipped with a water-cooled Peltier thermostatted cell holder. Fluorescence measurements were automatically recorded every 30 s while the cuvette was heated at a rate of 1 °C min⁻¹ from 25 to 85 °C. Melting curves were constructed using a Python script from time-resolved measurements of the sample fluorescence and temperature. The script returns the negative derivative of the fluorescence with respect to temperature. A Savitzky-Golay filter was applied using a fifth-order polynomial fit and an integration window of ten points. Multiple Gaussian curves were fitted to the melting curve in OriginPro 8.5 to approximate the average melting point of the samples.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16751724>, reference number 16751724.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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